

Membrane Potential of Manganese Ferrocyanide

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The present paper reports our results for the membrane potential of manganese ferrocyanide in presence of sodium and ammonium salts. The order is found to be $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$.

The results are in agreement with those of earlier workers.

The experimental details are as described in our earlier studies^{1,2}. The potentials developed and calculated ionic mobilities are recorded in Tables I, II, III & IV respectively.

TABLE I

Membrane potential of Manganese ferrocyanide using Sodium Salts

Concentration ratio	Potential (m.v.) in different electrolytes		
	NaCl	NaNO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₄
.2 & .02 M	9.8	14.2	16.8
.133 & .0133 M	16.0	17.0	19.0
.1 & .01 M	16.2	18.2	21.5
.04 & .004 M	16.5	20.0	22.1
.02 & .002 M	20.0	25.0	27.9
.01 & .001 M	26.9	27.6	30.5
.002 & .0002 M	33.5	34.0	35.4

TABLE II

Membrane potential of Manganese ferrocyanide using Ammonium Salts

Concentration ratio.	Potential (m.v.) in different electrolytes		
	NH ₄ Cl	NH ₄ NO ₃	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄
.2 & .02 M	14.4	15.4	17.3
.133 & .0133 M	18.7	20.0	20.6
.1 & .01 M	19.7	20.8	21.9
.04 & .004 M	20.5	21.0	22.5
.02 & .002 M	21.3	29.2	30.9
.01 & .001 M	30.7	34.2	34.7
.002 & .0002 M	35.4	37.0	37.8

1. K. K. Panday and V. K. Agrawal, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1968, 6(1), 48.

2. K. K. Panday and V. K. Agrawal, *Labdev J. Sci. & Tech.* (In Press).

TABLE III

Mobilities of Anions using Sodium Salts

Anions	True mobilities	Calculated mobilities at different concentrations				
		.2 & .02 M	.1 & .01 M	.02 & .002 M	.01 & .001 M	.002 & .0002 M
Cl^-	76.4	35.66	28.27	24.69	18.65	13.99
NO_3^-	71.5	29.55	25.50	19.82	17.86	13.58
$\frac{1}{2} \text{SO}_4^{2-}$	80.0	17.28	14.91	11.42	10.88	8.269

TABLE IV

Mobilities of Anions using Ammonium Salts

Anions	True mobilities	Calculated mobilities at different concentrations				
		.2 & .02 M	.1 & .01 M	.02 & .002 M	.01 & .001 M	.002 & .0002 M
Cl^-	76.4	39.11	32.15	30.23	20.33	16.12
NO_3^-	71.5	37.72	30.82	21.77	17.16	14.78
$\frac{1}{2} \text{SO}_4^{2-}$	80.0	28.68	23.26	15.01	12.19	10.16

DISCUSSION

The membrane potential of manganese ferrocyanide decreases in the order $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^-$ for sodium and ammonium salts at different concentrations.

Plots of potential versus time for $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4$ (Fig.) indicate that the ions are preferentially adsorbed at the surface of membrane, making it progressively more electro-negative in character. At a particular stage depending on the concentration of the electrolyte membrane assumes charge stability and similar potential values could be realized for the diffusion process (descending part of the curve) even after replacing the solution with the fresh solution or disturbing the position of the membrane. These results indicate that the membrane assumes equilibrium with the entire solution and once it has the charge stability, the geo-chemical effect described by Brauner⁶ is altogether absent.

The membrane potential is due to the preferential adsorption on the membrane³⁻⁵ surface is quite evident from the result obtained by us.

Earlier workers also obtained the similar results while studying permeability and adsorption.

3. H. B. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 335.
4. G. M. Willis, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1942, **38**, 169.
5. J. D. Tolliday, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, **45**, 148.
6. L. Brauner, *Koll. Beihefte.*, 1927, **23**, 143.

Fig. Plots of potential versus time using $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$

The mobility depends on two factors; firstly the formation of adsorptive layer on the surface of the membrane, secondly, diffused ionic atmosphere, which depends on the concentration of the electrolyte. The thickness of the ionic atmosphere would increase with the dilution, and would result in the great repulsion of anions. Thus the anions have the lowest mobilities, which is shown in table III and IV. The results are in agreement with the theory developed by Willis (*loc. cit.*).

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